

Novel Therapy and Diagnosis of Cervical Cancer Radio Resistance for the Future Development

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Background and introduction: Cervical cancer (CC) is the world's fourth most common malignancy in women, it is predicted that there will be roughly 798 thousand new cases per year during the next 20 years. In the developing world, to overcome this malignancy the standard treatment for cervical cancer is radiotherapy, either alone or in conjunction with chemotherapy. During their treatment, about 80% of cervical cancer patients got radiation therapy. Radio resistance, on the other hand, reduced overall survival.

Method: The method of this study is used to conduct online and a regular exploration of data bank like NCBI, PubMed, Embase, SCI Hub, google scholar, cross ref, and the Cochrane Library, using medical terminology like cellular stress with radioresistance where Radiation-induced damage responses cooperate to cause cancer cell death, but radiotherapy also activates damage-repair and survival signaling in a small percentage of cancer cells, alleviating radiation-induced cytotoxicity, and these activations are responsible for tumor radio-resistance. For diagnosis it is critical to investigate and develop more sensitive and specific DNA methylation techniques in order to improve cervical cancer early detection hypermethylation of SEPT9 has a high sensitivity and specificity.it could also improve cell resistance to ionizing radiation by changing the polarization of tumor-associated macrophages.

Conclusion: Traditional tumor therapy such as chemotherapy, targeted therapy, radiotherapy, surgery, and others, have been criticized in recent years for being slow and has limitations with side effects, to overcome these problems nanoparticles have the potential to not only address the inadequacies of traditional cancer diagnosis and treatment, but also to open entirely new avenues and develop cutting-edge technology for tumor detection and treatment. However, most nanoparticle research is conducted in vivo and in vitro, and only a few clinical studies on nanoparticles have been published.

Keywords: DIAGNOSIS, NOVEL THERAPY, CERVICAL CANCER, RADIORESISTANCES, TRADITIONAL THERAPY TARGETED THERAPY AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.

Introduction

Cervical cancer is one of the most common cancer-related deaths in women around the world. The standard treatment for cervical cancer is radiotherapy, either alone or in conjunction with chemotherapy. During their treatment, about 80% of cervical cancer patients got radiation therapy. Radio resistance, on the other hand, reduced overall survival. As a result, discovering and identifying novel tumorigenesis and radio resistance targets is critical for cervical cancer treatment. Cervical cancer is the fourth most frequent cancer in women, and it is also the fourth highest cause of cancer-related death. Some sexually transmitted diseases (HIV and Chlamydia trachomatis), smoking, a larger number of childbirths, and long-term use of oral contraceptives are also essential cofactors. Even though HPV vaccination and early screening programs have proven to be effective disease preventive methods¹, significant incidence rates are still seen in low- and middle-income countries. Even while the survival rate from cervical cancer has increased significantly in China, it is still lower than in certain advanced countries such as Canada, Norway and Australia.

Cervical cancer screening using a combination of cytology and HPV testing has lowered the incidence of cervical cancer², but cytological screening has a lower sensitivity than HPV testing. Radiotherapy is used to treat most individuals with invasive cervical cancer. Insensitivity to radiation, on the other hand, results in low efficacy. At this time, DNA methylation-based tests that can be utilized as a biomarker for the diagnosis of advanced CIN2/3 lesions, as well as several six methylated genes, such as SOX1, PAX1, JAM3, EPB41L3, CADM1, and MAL, have been characterized as promising indicators for the management of HPV-positive women³. It is critical to investigate and develop more sensitive and specific DNA methylation techniques in order to improve cervical cancer early detection. In the diagnosis of cervical cancer, hypermethylation of SEPT9 has a high sensitivity and specificity. Through the modulation of HMGB1, up- and down - regulation of SEPT9 influenced the biological behavior of cervical cancer cells. Furthermore, we identified that SEPT9-mediated miR-375 could improve cell resistance to ionizing radiation by changing the polarization of tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs)⁴.

SEPT9 hypermethylation distinguishes between cervical cancer and healthy tissues. The evidence indicates SEPT9 methylation could be used as a biomarker in the diagnosis of cervical cancer. By targeting the HMGB1-RB axis, it enhances cervical cancer growth and radio resistance, and by mediating miR-375, it causes macrophage polarization. SEPT9 may be a potential diagnostic and treatment biomarker for cervical cancer, according to our findings. Radiation resistance in tumor cells remains a significant therapeutic challenge. As a result, novel molecular targets must be discovered in order to understand the exact process of cervical cancer and determine radiation sensitivity. radio resistance is generally accepted as a major barrier in the treatment of cervical cancer. The HMGB3/hTERT signaling axis has been discovered as a new target for cervical cancer radio resistance⁵. Our findings provide light on the mechanism of cervical cancer radio resistance and suggest that targeting the HMGB3/hTERT signaling axis may be beneficial to patients with cervical cancer. As a result, it's essential to figure out the specific process of radiation resistance and possible targets. The HMGB3/hTERT signaling pathway has been discovered as a new target for cervical cancer radio resistance in this study. Along

with that we will also study about the recent hot topics such as immunotherapy, targeted therapy as well as nanoparticle for future development.

Materials and methods

Literature review:

The following search strategy is used to conduct online and a regular exploration of data bank like NCBI PubMed, Embase, SCI Hub, google scholar, cross ref, and the Cochrane Library, using medical terminology and the specific keywords. this study is based on the latest information up to date publication about diagnosis, immunotherapy and novel therapy of cervical cancer radio resistance for the future development.

Cellular stress with Radio-resistance:

One of the most common cancer treatments is radiotherapy. Because of the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), DNA damage, subcellular organelle destruction, and autophagy, cellular stress is caused by penetrating radiation, either directly or indirectly. Radiation-induced damage responses cooperate to cause cancer cell death, but radiotherapy also activates damage-repair and survival signaling in a small percentage of cancer cells, alleviating radiation-induced cytotoxicity, and these activations are responsible for tumor radio-resistance⁶. Cancer cells that have acclimated to intratumorally hypoxia may be driven by the HIF1 response, which involves metabolic reprogramming and survival signaling, and so gain the ability to withstand radiation-induced cytotoxicity. The activation of the UPR and cytoprotective autophagy reduces the radiation-induced damage response and consequently contributes to radio resistance by recovering unfolded proteins and recycling malfunctioned subcellular organelles. Although tumor radio resistance is still a problem, pre-clinical and clinical efforts in radiation oncology, such as combinatorial chemotherapeutic therapies with or without hyperthermia, have increased treatment success. In various tumor microenvironments, more research on the pharmacological uses of molecular radiosensitizers in conjunction with or without hyperthermia is needed.

The above diagram is searched online through google on cellular stress in cervical cancer and resistance to therapy. Link, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/cms/asset/a1769270-7ddf-4722-91da-261d6345c357/jcb28007-fig-0002-m.jpg>.

Diagnosis:

Cervical cancer is the third most prevalent cancer in women globally, and the disease is caused by a chronic infection with the high-risk human papillomavirus (HR-HPV). Although HR-HPV infections are widespread, only around 10% of them survive, with a subset of them driving the progression of occult precursors to cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grades 2 and 3 (CIN2/3) and subsequently cervical cancer. Due to its great sensitivity, lack of morphology preservation requirements, and low cost. For CIN screening, HR-HPV testing is becoming the recommended technique. However, because only a small percentage of HR-HPV positive women develop clinically significant lesions, cytology is still used as the primary screening test. As a supplement to HR-HPV testing, new diagnostic biomarkers with high specificity are desired⁷. The development of a simple molecular triage test is especially anticipated since it may be more readily applied in less developed countries and in vaginal self-collected specimens, resulting in a significant reduction in cervical cancer mortality globally. Several methylation genes have shown potential in identifying CIN2/3, with EPB41L3 appearing to be the most promising. Combining methylated human gene biomarkers may be clinically effective for triaging women with HR-HPV infections.

Based on the increased or decreased levels of many miRNAs discovered in cervical cancer patients, miRNA may have a role in the disease's etiology. Cervical cancer has a wide range of clinical outcomes that are difficult

to predict. Because most cervix biopsies are tiny, one specific obstacle in cervical cancer biomarker research is the absence of substantial quantities of tumor material. Because RNA degrades quickly when transported into blood due to RNases, it was thought that miRNA could not be identified in serum. Exosomes and granular vesicles circulating in blood were later shown to contain released miRNAs. The discovery that miRNA can alter HPV DNA replication adds to our knowledge of the HPV life cycle and the mechanisms behind HPV-induced oncogenesis⁸.

Also, miRNA processing proteins may also have a role in the early stages of cervical cancer development. Overexpression of DNA methyltransferase enzymes, which can catalyze aberrant methylation of protein-coding and miRNA genes, could be induced by HPV's E6 and E7 oncoproteins. Analysis of variations in the levels of certain miRNAs in serum and identification of abnormal hypermethylation of miRNAs are used to diagnose cervical cancer. Cervical cancer screening using a combination of cytology and HPV testing has lowered the incidence of cervical cancer, but cytological screening has a lower sensitivity than HPV testing. Radiotherapy is used to treat most individuals with invasive cervical cancer. Insensitivity to radiation, on the other hand, results in low efficacy⁹. With high sensitivity and specificity (AUC = 0.854 and 0.797, respectively, P less than 0.001), hyper-methylation of SEPT9 detects cervical cancer and normal tissues, normal+CIN1 and CIN2+CIN3+cancer. When compared to para-carcinomatous tissues, SEPT9 mRNA and protein expression was elevated in cervical cancer tissues. SEPT9 enhances cervical cancer cell proliferation, invasion, and migration, as well as influencing the cell cycle. Irradiation resistance is increased when SEPT9 interacts with the HMGB1-RB axis. Furthermore, SEPT9 polarized miR-375 through tumor associated macrophages (TAMs), altering radiation resistance in cervical carcinoma. SEPT9 methylation could be a biomarker for cervical cancer diagnosis, accordingly Via targeting the HMGB1-RB axis, it increases cervical cancer growth and radio resistance, meanwhile another study suggests that a panel of three miRNAs is required for CIN3 in hr HPV-positive scrapes and can be used in conjunction with DNA methylation studies to detect cervical malignancy. The combined analysis of the two marker types should be investigated further as a triage technique in hrHPV-based screening¹⁰.

Another study shows a method of detecting cervical cancer by Different miRNAs were detected in cervical mucus samples collected using a non-invasive approach. To do so, they compared data from a typical PAP-smear brush used for cytology and a therapeutically utilized cotton swab to miRNA expression data. At Germany, both procedures are used in different labs and clinics. The PAP-smear brush enabled a more substantial and reliable detection of miRNAs, according to preliminary results¹¹. There is another study called pooled study according to them SOX14 methylation levels were considerably higher in cervical squamous cell carcinoma and endocervical adenocarcinoma (CESC) compared to normal tissues (P 0.001). SOX14 hypermethylation has been linked to cervical cancer and could be used as a molecular biomarker for cervical cancer screening and early detection¹².

Li et al suggest DNA methylation markers have been investigated as possible biomarkers for the early diagnosis of cervical cancer. The diagnostic effectiveness of zinc finger protein 582 (ZNF582) methylation for cervical

cancer detection was investigated in this study. The methylation of ZNF582 has the potential to be used as an auxiliary biomarker for cervical cancer screening. In cervical scrapings, a new technique of co-testing HPV DNA and ZNF582 methylation test improves diagnostic accuracy over single HPV DNA testing¹³. New ideas and methodologies have emerged as a result of recent discoveries, which have aided in the understanding of the relationship between epigenetics and tumor biology. The science of tumor genetics has now grown to incorporate a novel type of epigenetic regulation. The relevance of DNA methylation and hydroxy methylation in certain genes in the progression of cervical cancer has been revealed in a growing number of research. Identifying these genes' methylation and hydroxy methylation profiles will aid in early detection and diagnosis, as well as monitoring recurrence of cervical cancer¹⁴.

Zhang et al published a paper in 2021 according to that study The methylation of the ZNF582 gene and tissue protein expression can be utilized to screen for cervical cancer with excellent sensitivity and specificity. We looked at the link between ZNF582 gene promoter methylation and cervical cancer and high-risk HPV16/18 infection. Although the ZNF582 protein is abundant in cervical cancer tissues, it is insufficient for use as a cervical cancer staging criteria. ZNF582 promoter methylation, on the other hand, demonstrated great specificity and sensitivity in detecting CIN2 and highly diseased cervical lesions, suggesting that it could be employed as a diagnostic marker for cervical cancer in women.¹⁵

Google link: <https://images.app.goo.gl/SKu9ki6RYFuEWVbj6>.

Novel therapy:

Advanced cervical cancer is still a difficult problem to cure. Chemoradiotherapy followed by brachytherapy is the current standard of care, however it is linked with significant toxicity¹⁶. Induction chemotherapy has a full pathologic response rate of 11 percent to 20 percent¹⁷. Because cancer cells are resistant to chemotherapy treatments and their maximal concentration within a tumor is low, there is no difference in survival benefit between chemotherapy, surgery, or radiotherapy alone¹⁸. These drawbacks are eliminated by isolated hypoxic perfusion. We present three patients with advanced cervical carcinomas of histologic grade G3 who refused standard treatment and chose isolated hypoxic pelvic perfusion instead (HPP). The PROCESS criteria were used to report this current case series¹⁹.

The standard of care for advanced cervical cancer treatment is chemoradiotherapy followed by intracavitary

brachytherapy. Long-term disease-free survival (DFS) is estimated to be between 85 and 90%. Due to the toxicity of platinum-based regimens and the mutilating effect of radiation, it is unfortunately linked with high morbidity. Vaginal dryness, ureteral strictures, vesicovaginal and rectovaginal fistulas, lymph stasis, and lymphocele are only a few of the symptoms. None of our patients have had any of these negative effects. Induction chemotherapy and subsequent radical surgery have a lower DFS than cisplatin-based chemoradiotherapy and radical surgery²⁰. Intensity-modulated radiation therapy lowered toxicity by about 50%, but it still causes severe side effects in about 30% of patients²¹.

We come to conclusion that HPP was shown to be effective in establishing complete and long-lasting clinical and radiologic remission with no evidence of systemic damage. Prospective randomized trial comparing the present standard of care to isolated hypoxia perfusion is required²².

Novel therapeutic strategy for cervical cancer:

Patients with cervical cancer now have more treatment choices thanks to the rapid development of radiation and innovative targeted medicines. However, due to the recurrence and metastasis of cervical cancer, mostly due to radio resistance²³, clinical results have only improved somewhat.

Here is another publication from CHICHAO FU.

CXCL12 expression is suppressed by siRNA. RNA interference was used to reduce the amount of expression of CXCL12. Hela cells were transfected with three distinct designed siRNAs as well as nonsense siRNA. CXCL12 mRNA expression was evaluated by RT-qPCR 24 hours after transfection. CXCL12 protein expression was measured by ELISA 48 hours after transfection on cell supernatants. In the presence of the three chosen siRNA, CXCL12 mRNA and protein expression levels were significantly reduced (P less than 0.05). The cells treated with CXCL12-siRNA2 had the lowest levels of CXCL12 expression. As a result, CXCL12-siRNA2 was used in subsequent investigations²⁴.

Finally, stimulation of the CXCL12/CXCR4 axis is crucial for radio resistance in cervical cancer. CD44 could also play a role in the process. Further research into the mechanisms of the CXCL12/CXCR4 axis in radio resistance is needed in the future to better understand the effects of the tumor environment on radio resistance and develop novel therapeutic options for cervical cancer. The DNA damage repair-associated gene Helicase-like transcription factor (HLTF), which is implicated in radio-resistance, is targeted by miR-145, according to our findings. Furthermore, overexpression of miR-145 in cervical cancer cells increases radiosensitivity both in vitro and in vivo. These findings suggest that focusing on miR-145 could be a potential radio sensitization strategy for cervical cancer.

About the novel therapy Chunyan Liu et al also said that UBE2R2-AS1 inhibited the biological activities of cervical cancer cells, suggesting that it could be used as an anti-tumor factor²⁵.

Zhang et al also describe that SLC16A1-AS1 was shown to be downregulated in CSCC and was linked to a poor prognosis. SLC16A1-AS1 overexpression may prevent cervical cancer cells from proliferating.

Furthermore, SLC16A1-AS1 may sponge miR-194 and raise SOCS2 expression levels, preventing cervical cancer cells from proliferating²⁶.

Through the miR-194/SOCS2 axis, SLC16A1-AS1 was downregulated in CSCC and reduced cell proliferation in cervical squamous cell carcinoma (CSCC).

Radiotherapy is an important part of the treatment of cervical cancer, however current radiosensitizers have poor clinical efficacy. Remember that in cervical cancer cells, DHO (dihydroouaba) increased radiosensitivity considerably. Radiation-induced S phase arrest in cervical cancer cells was also prevented. The combination treatment resulted in significant suppression of Chk1 and an increase in DNA double-strand breaks (DSB).

DHO is a new radiosensitizer that can be used to treat cervical cancer. The study's automated high-throughput screening platform proved to be powerful and effective, having the potential to be widely employed in the future for radiosensitizer identification²⁷.

The typical treatment for CC at stages IB2 to IVA is a combination of radiotherapy and chemotherapy. Pelvic external beam radiation therapy (EBRT), intracavitary brachytherapy with cisplatin, or cisplatin and 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) chemotherapy are some of these methods. Endogenous wild-type p53 activation is required for radio/chemotherapy-induced cytotoxicity, according to both experimental and clinical investigations, while p53 inactivation has been linked to treatment resistance or insensitivity²⁸. The following is the diagram from google.

Google link:3. <https://images.app.goo.gl/P5oSbQd9jdL3Qzah6>.

Nanoparticle new approach to cervical cancer for the future:

Traditional cancer treatments have been criticized for a variety of side effects and insufficient tumor destruction.

The development of nanoparticles has opened a new avenue for improving traditional therapies and diagnostics.

In fact, nanoparticles have the potential to not only address the inadequacies of traditional cancer diagnosis and treatment, but also to open entirely new avenues and develop cutting-edge technology for tumor detection and treatment. However, most nanoparticle research is conducted *in vivo* and *in vitro*, and only a few clinical studies on nanoparticles have been published.

Traditional tumor treatments, such as chemotherapy, targeted therapy, radiotherapy, surgery, and others, have been criticized in recent years for being slow to develop and for causing numerous undesirable reactions and unsatisfactory treatment outcomes. Due to the limitations of standard tumor therapies, a growing number of studies are looking for new tumor therapeutics with better targeting, tumor stem cell destruction, and fewer side effects. Immunotherapy, targeted therapy, physical ablation, gene therapy, photodynamic therapy (PDT), and photothermal therapy (PTT) are examples of new tumor treatment strategies that have shown higher success as compared to traditional tumor treatments.

All the therapy techniques described here have one thing in common: they all require carrier cooperation. Viruses can be utilized as carriers, but they have been proven to produce intracellular mutagenesis and immunogenicity. As a result, developing a carrier that is both safer and more effective has been a primary focus²⁹. Nanoparticles are rapidly being used as carriers in new tumor treatment strategies because to their small size, biosafety, drug loading, and physical qualities, which can aid physical therapy. These nanoparticle-mediated medicines offer the advantages of being multifunctional, having fewer side effects, and having a better curative impact. Furthermore, several medical imaging modalities mediated by nanoparticles have improved clarity and accuracy, allowing for more accurate tumor identification and treatment³⁰.

Google link4. <https://images.app.goo.gl/2wzT2xCvgq4TPPSm7>

Conclusion

According to the current evidence in year 2021, cervical cancer is the fourth most diagnosed malignancy in women and the fourth major cause of cancer mortality. As we know that the standard treatment for cervical cancer is radiotherapy, either alone or in combination with chemotherapy about 80% of cervical cancer patients got radiation therapy, but on the other side radio resistance reduced overall survival. Even though HPV vaccination and early screening programs have proven to be effective disease preventive methods and a combination of cytology and HPV testing has lowered the incidence of cervical cancer, but cytological screening has a lower sensitivity than HPV testing.

At this time, DNA methylation-based tests that can be utilized as a biomarker for the diagnosis of advanced CIN2/3 lesions, as well as several six methylated genes, with high sensitivity and specificity SEPT9 hypermethylation distinguishes between cervical cancer and healthy tissues. SEPT9 enhances cervical cancer cell proliferation, invasion, and migration, as well as influencing the cell cycle. Irradiation resistance is

increased when SEPT9 interacts with the HMGB1-RB axis. Furthermore, SEPT9 polarized miR-375 through tumor associated macrophages (TAMs), altering radiation resistance in cervical carcinoma. and by mediating miR-375, it causes macrophage polarization. SEPT9 may be a potential diagnostic and treatment biomarker for cervical cancer, The evidence indicates SEPT9 methylation could be used as therapeutic biomarker in the diagnosis of cervical cancer.

As a result, novel molecular targets have been discovered in this study to understand the exact process of cervical cancer and determine radiation sensitivity. Our findings also provide light on the mechanism of cervical cancer radio resistance and suggest that targeting the HMGB3/hTERT signaling axis may be beneficial to patients with cervical cancer. The HMGB3/hTERT signaling axis has been discovered as a new target for cervical cancer radio resistance.

On the other side when we come to novel therapy, chemoradiotherapy followed by brachytherapy is the current standard of care, however it is linked with significant toxicity.to overcome these problems we come to conclusion of nanoparticle therapeutic strategy for the present and future treatment of cervical cancer.

Traditional tumor treatments, such as chemotherapy, targeted therapy, radiotherapy, surgery, and others, have been criticized in recent years for being slow to develop and for causing numerous undesirable reactions and unsatisfactory treatment outcomes. Due to the limitations of standard tumor therapies, a growing number of studies are looking for new tumor therapeutics with better targeting, tumor stem cell destruction, and fewer side effects.

The development of nanoparticles has opened a new avenue for improving traditional therapies and diagnostics. In fact, nanoparticles have the potential to not only address the inadequacies of traditional cancer diagnosis and treatment, but also to open entirely new avenues and develop cutting-edge technology for tumor detection and treatment. However, most nanoparticle research is conducted in vivo and in vitro, and only a few clinical studies on nanoparticles have been published.

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